

DIVERSIFICATION IS AN IMPORTANT PRINCIPLE OF CONTINUOUS EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the principle of diversification, the needs, necessity and possibilities of its implementation in the educational system. Opinions are given about the role and importance of our country in the education system, in particular, in higher education.

Today, a number of reforms are being implemented in all areas. At the same time, various new concepts, approaches and principles are being introduced in the field of education as a target of reforms. One such principle - the process of diversification is one of the new concepts entering the education system today. The process of diversification in the countries of the world began to develop from the mid-50s of the 20th century. Initially, in the USA, Japan, and Western European countries, diversification occurs in the fields of industry, transport, construction, and finance. Therefore, this concept was first widely used in the economic sphere, and its content can be summarized as diversification (Latin *diversificatio* - change, diverse development) by a manufacturer or trader by introducing new products to expand the range of production or trade is given. By diversifying production, firms enter new sectors and regions, expand the types of goods, and

gradually turn into multi-industry complexes[1].

Based on this definition, we can define the content of the concept of diversification in education as follows: on the one hand, it is the possibility of multifaceted organization of educational institutions that maximally satisfy the needs of society and production, and on the other hand, the interests and needs of the individual. the principle of establishing an educational system that provides, that is, leaving the unified state education system. Or the principle of organizing the education system in the conditions of democracy and market. This principle ensures the diversity, versatility and variability of the development of educational institutions and their management bodies. At the same time, the complexity of the internal infrastructure of the education system: emergence of new types and types of educational institutions; penetration of some forms of education into others; combinations of different types, types and forms of education that

were previously unrelated; expanding the scope of activities of educational institutions; diversity of content of educational programs; freedom to use educational technologies; It represents the distribution of influence on different sectors of society[2].

As a manifestation of the principle of diversification, private educational institutions have appeared in the educational system along with state educational institutions. In addition, lyceums, gymnasiums, colleges, educational centers and the lower system of education, etc. were established. In order to increase children's access to preschool education, the system of organizing private and family kindergartens began to form. Based on these, we can say that the diversification of the education system is a process aimed at creating optimal conditions for meeting the various educational needs, interests and expectations of citizens.

The process of diversification has entered the education system of our country and is showing its results. We know that Uzbekistan is a demographically fast-growing country with a young population. Every year, more than 600,000 people, most of whom are graduates of secondary special educational institutions, express their desire to enter higher education institutions. However, statistics of recent years have shown that higher education institutions cover only 9-10% of them. According to the initiative of the President of our Republic, Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, this year, due to the diversification of the forms and directions of higher education, first of all, the introduction of evening and part-time forms of education, compared to last year, an increase in admission to higher

education institutions was achieved by 30%. As we said above, diversification in education is considered in some sense as a process aimed at creating optimal conditions for satisfying the various educational needs, interests and expectations of citizens, so such activities carried out at the initiative of the head of state are in some sense the principle of diversification. shows its actual application. In addition, the Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the activities of the center for the development of higher education and the implementation of advanced technologies" defines the main tasks of the Center, one of which is its departmental subordination and expansion (diversification) of the types of educational services in the educational-methodical field, aimed at increasing the competitiveness of republican higher education institutions, regardless of ownership forms.

The principle of innovative structuring of the educational system, ensuring the possibility of changing educational services and the programs, types and forms of educational organizations are considered as the diversification of modern education. If the first stage of diversification of the education system is related to the increase in the number of educational institutions and students, now the first stage of diversification of the higher education system in our country is gaining momentum. The next stage, in turn, begins with solving meaningful problems. That is, processes related to bringing the quality and content of education to a new level. Diversification reflects the formation of a new educational paradigm that focuses more on the individual than on production.

It describes the increase in the level of flexibility of the educational system, its ability to be quickly reconstructed, the need to take into account the growing demands of society for the results of the educational system. Education, which until recently was a "stronghold of personnel", is gradually turning into a sphere of people's design of their lives, creation of ideas and plans, which are then implemented in life[3].

At the same time, the process of diversification is a phenomenon that is considered as a holistic pedagogical process, which includes not only the strategic directions of educational development and the change of educational institutions, but also continuous education in the field of existing educational policy, the establishment of a new one. , the content of educational programs, educational technologies, educational forms, educational services, etc. will be expanded.

All this provides an opportunity for communication between students, helps to create a special atmosphere - an atmosphere of intellectual and emotional comfort.

What forces us to change the way we organize our education system?" the question arises. The educational information received by the student quickly becomes outdated, it "falls behind"

the practice of implementing educational services in society. In addition, the traditional content of education given by the teacher does not always adequately reflect reality.

The labor market is putting new demands on the training of specialists who can quickly and successfully adapt to difficult conditions and make the right decisions. Today's student is tomorrow's professional. He must do his duty responsibly.

Another reason for the need for diversification is the change in the demand of the wider society, the employer, as diverse educational applicants.

The third factor affecting the change in the principles of the educational system organization is the democratic conditions in education, which are logically strengthened by changes in the legal framework.

Successfully solving the tactical tasks of reforms in the higher education system implies the modernization of its leading components, including educational standards, organizational-management structure, educational content and technology, quality control of personnel training, etc.

Thus, diversification of education is a rapidly developing process today, and its implementation in higher education has its positive effect.

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